

Message from the Guest Editor

Keiji Fujiyoshi
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XX ISA World Congress of Sociology was held from June 25 to July 1, 2023 in Melbourne, Australia and it was a great success. According to the ISA statistics, it had 4,701 participants (3,028 in-person and 1,673 virtual)². RC25 hosted nine sessions, six joint sessions, co-hosted four joint sessions (with RC05 Racism, Nationalism, Indigeneity and Ethnicity, RC15 Sociology of Health, RC30 Sociology of Work, and TG04 Sociology of Risk and Uncertainty), and also had a business meeting, which was a huge success. We served as Program Coordinators together with Frida Petersson, Sweden, who virtually participated in the Congress.

After the wonderful success in Melbourne, we have been invited to take a role of guest editors of the special issue of LD&S by Anna Odrowaz-Coates, its Editor-in-Chief. We are so pleased to share some of the insightful and stimulating discussions there with you. Also, we express our sincere gratitude to the contributors.

Here is the Call for Papers published in the Q4, 2023 issue of the RC25 newsletter.

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CALL FOR PAPERS for June 2024 ISSUE of LDS – Melbourne World Congress of Sociology

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Although we receive a steady flow of papers (more contributions than we can process), we wish to offer to fast-track the articles based on presentations from the RC25 sessions in Melbourne.

IMPORTANT DATES:

- 31st of December 2023: Due date for submission
- February-March 2024: Feedback from the reviewers
- March-April 2024: Submission of the revised articles
- June 2024: Publication of the special issue

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This thematic issue from the Melbourne World Congress of Sociology will be published in June 2024.

Thank you for responding to the call.

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² <https://www.isa-sociology.org/en/conferences/world-congress/melbourne-2023/statistics-23>